

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6613579>

УДК 334.78

CONVERGING COMPETENCES OF SCIENTIFIC ORGANIZATIONS AND INTERDISCIPLINARY PRIORITIES OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: Breakthrough research and development is impossible without the implementation of modern tools to support managerial decision-making. An integral part of the research activities convergence is the creation of algorithmic and information-measuring support. Software has been developed for assessing the discriminability of an interdisciplinary study, which allows to clearly compare the target orientation of the study and the indicators that are used to form specialized scientific organizations. The software allows to determine the impact of the scientific and technological potential of research organizations, namely competence and competency on the scientific performance qualitative indicators.

Keywords: scientific organizations, interdisciplinary research, artificial intelligence, convergence, scientific and technological development

The concept of development and informatization involves the use of the latest progressive technologies encourages the development of new forms of knowledge representation using modern intelligent decision support systems [1, 2].

However, at present, simple computerization and informatization is not enough to ensure the quality and efficiency of the research process. Research results, which are determined, in particular, by the level of competence of scientific organizations, are considered as some measurable value, for the evaluation of which scientifically based methods should be involved, and the obtained values should be accompanied by an assessment of their accuracy. At the same time, the quality of measuring the level of performance is directly determined by the quality of the tools that were used during the study and evaluation of the scientific result

itself [3, 4]. Scientometric databases are currently considered the most effective and objective means of assessing scientific performance, as evidenced by their prevalence in various areas of scientific results verification [5, 6]. At the same time, only intelligent systems that have passed the scientifically based stages of development and verification of quality indicators can provide objective characteristics of the interdisciplinary research implementation scientific effectiveness.

Quite a lot of publications are devoted to the solution of such issues as the choice of an indicators' list that should characterize the quality of scientific results, methods for their evaluation, as well as determining their practical value [7, 8]. However, despite the diversity of opinions and approaches, a general concept on these issues has not yet been developed. The quality of an intellectual system for the convergence of the competencies of scientific organizations and interdisciplinary priorities of scientific and technological development is laid at the stages of project development and strategic calculation, and is controlled at the stage of a pilot experiment and monitoring of scientific performance. At the same time, such quality indicators as the reliability and criterion validity of the goals and objectives of interdisciplinary research, the difficulty and discriminability of interdisciplinary research methods are subject to control. At the same time, the assessment of these indicators should be carried out using the developed information-measuring system that implements tasks from collecting scientific data, processing them, combining them, checking them with established standards, to issuing reasonable recommendations for improving the decision support system.

The possibility of implementing an interdisciplinary research is an indicator of the quality of an intellectual system that characterizes the sensitivity of the procedure for validating the competencies of a scientific organization. This indicator was studied in two aspects.

The first is related to the fact that discriminability is considered as a characteristic of each scientific subtask of interdisciplinary research. This approach is used both in the theory of processing the results of scientific research, and for modeling and parametrization of the scientific and technological development directions.

The second approach is related to the assessment of the discriminability of interdisciplinary research as a whole. Empirical distributions of research results are considered and discriminability conclusions are obtained based on the analysis of the shape of the distribution curve. Discriminability is considered as a gradation on the scale of latent parameters.

The discriminability index of scientific subtasks and interdisciplinary research is of particular importance when using normative-oriented projects. When using criteria-oriented projects, this indicator is not always decisive. However, even when implementing criteria-oriented projects, the discriminability of

scientific subtasks should be taken into account at the stage of developing a research space, since it determines the sensitivity of the convergence procedure. Information about the value of the discriminability makes it possible to increase the sensitivity of the convergence procedure on certain ranges of the studied property scale of a scientific problem by selecting the appropriate subtasks. Therefore, along with the indicator of the difficulty of scientific subtasks, the discriminability can be used in the implementation of interdisciplinary research in an adaptive mode.

The choice of methods, approaches, models and tools for solving the problem to assess the discriminability, which use assessment methods based on the analysis of the consistency (or contrast) of experimental data obtained from the results of an interdisciplinary study. In this case, the discriminability can be estimated both for the entire sample and for its parts. It is proposed to estimate the discriminability of problems in the scientific and technological space on the basis of the multisets metric spaces methodology [9, 10].

The multisets spaces metrics are adequate for operating with quantities represented by the order scale. Qualitative methods of pairwise comparison impose significant limitations, in particular, regarding the size of the studied sample and the type of its distribution [11, 12]. The accuracy of the indicator estimation can be improved by accumulating and jointly processing experimental data. Taking into account the fact that qualitative ranks are the numbers of elements of the studied series and represent elements of the ordinal scale, the medians of the series are used as central trends.

Discriminability evaluation of an interdisciplinary study by the coefficient of connection qualitative assessments are divided: into three parts: "weak" – with the lowest primary estimates, "medium" and "strong" – with the highest primary estimates. Next, the multisets multiplicity of falling into the corresponding group is used.

Various coefficients determine the type and "strength" of the connection based on the multiplicity values. The consistency ratio is a measure of two-way communication. Belonging to a certain group ("strong" or "weak") scientific organizations may be primary, and the solution of a scientific subtask may be a dependent factor. To evaluate the measure of association, the convergence coefficient is estimated.

The used metrics of multisets spaces are adequate to operating with the values represented by the order scale. Moreover, the ranking places of scientific subtasks for each coefficient are preserved.

The discriminability power of an interdisciplinary study is considered in two aspects: the discriminability of the study as a whole, as a parameter of a two-parameter model; the competence of a scientific organization, as a gradation of division on a scale of potential levels. Graphically, the discriminability parameter is represented by the slope of the tangent of the success function at the inflection

point. This parameter can take values from -1 to 1. The parameter is evaluated in relative units and must not be less than 0.

The discriminability of an interdisciplinary study as a whole is interpreted as a gradation of division on a scale of latent parameters. The numerical characteristic of the discriminability indicator depends on the number of scientific subtasks and cannot be less than two neighboring values of the level of competence on the gradation scale in this range.

An analysis of the considered metrics made it possible to choose those that can be used to train intelligent decision support systems during trial operation. The discriminability, which is determined by the method of contrast groups, requires significant amounts of experimental data and has limitations on the form of their distribution. Therefore, this method can be used when accumulating significant amounts of experimental data during the interdisciplinary research implementation monitoring.

The association and consistency coefficients of the multisets multiplicities were used, which have different sensitivity in different gradations of the qualitative scale. The contingency coefficient, in contrast to the coefficients of association and consistency, characterizing a one-way relationship, characterizes a two-way relationship. Since empirical data are measured on an order scale, the choice of sensitivity characteristics in different gradations of the scale is not decisive. At the same time, when studying discriminability, one-way linking is important. Therefore, to calculate the discriminability of scientific subtasks during trial operation, the contingency coefficient is also used. Another significant advantage of using the multiset metric for multiplicity factors is the ability to calculate the uncertainty of the estimate of this indicator, which is lacking in traditional quantitative measures of linking in interval scales. Therefore, the coefficients of metric spaces of multisets were used to assess the interdisciplinary research discriminability both in assessing competencies and in the process of assessing the competence of scientific organizations.

Confirmation of the quality of the conduct and results of an interdisciplinary study is largely determined by the qualitative indicators of the tools with which this quality is assessed. Therefore, the creation of algorithmic and information-measuring support for assessing the quality indicators of intelligent decision support systems is an integral part of the convergence of research activities. Software has been developed for assessing the discriminability of an interdisciplinary study, which allows to clearly compare the target orientation of the study and the indicators that are used to form a group of specialized scientific organizations. The software makes it possible to determine the impact of the scientific and technological potential of research organizations, namely competence and competency, on the qualitative indicators of scientific performance.

The disadvantages of existing software systems is the lack of modules for the exchange of scientific information between organizations of different profiles, which makes it impossible to process interdisciplinary experimental data. An information-measuring system has been developed to control the parameters of the scientific and technical potential. A feature of the system is the information model of the restored scientific and technological environment, which allows to dynamically adjust the parameters depending on the needs of the science-intensive industry in different periods of development and regardless of external conditions. The information model highlights the range of parameters that most affect scientific performance and ensure high quality indicators of scientific research. Existing decision support systems require a change in the experimental model and improvement of technical means for obtaining and processing scientific information [13, 14].

An intelligent decision support system has been developed to study the influence of the competencies of scientific organizations on the quality of solving interdisciplinary research problems. The system provides for the collection of experimental data, their transfer to the server, storage in a database and subsequent analytical processing. To collect experimental data, combined algorithms for qualitative analysis of solutions are used, which provide sufficiently high speed and acceptable accuracy of the results obtained. The decision support system makes it possible to unambiguously determine the competencies of a scientific organization for solving interdisciplinary research problems. The information is stored in a relational database management system. Additionally, the server software allows for analytical processing of experimental data to create models of scientific and technological development and the impact of the competencies of scientific organizations on the quality of scientific results and, accordingly, the assessment of competency.

It is possible to assess the competence of a scientific organization using the method of presenting this characteristic. Therefore, first of all, the task is reduced to building a competence model. In this situation, it is useful to conduct a simulation experiment, the essence of which is the artificial reproduction of a sample of empirical data, for which the profile of "correct" estimates is known in advance, noises are superimposed, the nature of which in each individual process makes it possible to simulate one or another type of behavior of interdisciplinary research.

Simulation models and, consequently, simulation modeling technologies differ significantly from cognitive and predictive models, the use of which has always been subject to a certain, previously known goal [15, 16]. Simulation models by their nature can be designated as research models, because one of the areas of their application is to determine the possible goal of system development [17, 18]. By changing certain characteristics of the system during the simulation

experience, it is possible to study different scenarios for the development of events, analyze the range of probable strategies for the system development, and choose a scenario of events that is more effective according to a certain criterion [19, 20].

In the implemented intelligent decision support system, production models of expert knowledge are presented. The system allows to process data and compare the result with the real competence profile of a scientific organization.

The developed models of expert knowledge were formalized in the form of a knowledge base that satisfies the following principles:

- should be based on qualitative data, in particular on the qualitative profile of the scientific organization's competencies;
- verified training samples, which should be obtained from the analysis of assessments of previous experience in the implementation of research tasks;
- assessments of the competencies of scientific organizations will differ only due to random components, that is, the boundaries and density of distribution of points of a multisets metric spaces cluster will depend only on the form of multiplicity distribution.

Implemented the ability to select scientific organizations and scientific subtasks depending on the profile. Then standards are set – the best values for each empirical study. The results of scientific research obtained from scientific organizations with a low level of competence may contain large errors, when calculated using existing quantitative averaging methods, leading to significant shifts in the mean. The proposed qualitative methods of competence analysis are free from these shortcomings. If, after applying the noise, the estimate is outside the qualitative scale, it is reduced to the nearest multiplicity bound of the multiset.

The applied methods of qualitative classification make it possible to classify scientific organizations characterized by many qualitative features in relation to the competencies significance level. The results of clustering, i.e. groups or clusters can be interpreted according to a given classification according to a scientific profile. Separate scientific organizations can be combined to solve an interdisciplinary problem. This is useful in cases where the combined efforts of scientific organizations can achieve synergy of various competencies. When applying cluster analysis, such organizations form separate interdisciplinary clusters depending on the model of managing the scientific research implementation.

The article is prepared with the financial support of the Russian Science Foundation, project № 19-78-10055.

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Поступила в редакцию 11.04.2022

Принята к публикации 25.04.2022

Для цитирования:

Pronichkin S.V., Gayer A.V., Chernyshova Y.S. Converging competences of scientific organizations and interdisciplinary priorities of scientific and technological development // Инновационные научные исследования. 2022. № 4-2(18). С. 135-142. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>